

Sustainable Economic Perspective: A Commitment to Agriculture in Latin American Countries

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ABSTRACT

This document aims to find a space for reflection and analysis from a sustainable economic perspective, thus, the challenges that are part of agriculture in Latin American countries impact economic sectors and promote the creation of marketing strategies. This includes a vision of the challenges and opportunities that sustainable agriculture has in a commitment to the creation of green jobs and the strengthening of communities. The research method considered involves the preliminary and critical review of the literature, favoring the reflective analysis of its relationship with key aspects such as sustainable agriculture and economic development in the populations of Latin America, providing a place of tension and meeting for discussion, about the sustainable agriculture alternatives, that nations actually use to improve a notable increase in economic indices and expand market options in Latin American countries.

KEYWORDS: Agriculture, Green Jobs, Economy, Sustainable and Latin America

I. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability continues to be the economic bet of culturally agricultural Latin American countries. Furthermore, the implementation of an agricultural economy is conceived, which is capable of bringing countries considered to be third world closer to the path of transformation, supported by an economy based on the development of sustainable agriculture; These nations seek to balance economic growth with environmental protection and try to find themselves on the same path as highly industrialized countries.

Now, the proclamation of a “green economy” suggests that the paradigm shift is necessary to promote an environmental protection policy that can generate possibilities for economic growth. This indicates that sustainability is not understood as a challenge that impedes the economic development of nations, but, on the contrary, is configured as the belief system that drives creativity, in science, technology and innovation.

This reflection pays close attention, to the most relevant information in relation to aspects such as; the *Challenges and Opportunities for agriculture* in Developing Countries, it also shows a clear selection of *Key Concepts such as Sustainable Agriculture and Economic Development* and highlights *Job Creation greens and the strengthening of*

rural communities. through which a detailed analysis of this topic is carried out and the importance of adopting innovative and sustainable approaches that not only boost economic growth, but also preserve natural resources for future generations is revealed.

Likewise, it is intended to address some concerns that arise within the framework of the path towards sustainable agriculture, about the way in which sustainable agriculture alternatives can improve economic development in Latin American nations, which lays the foundations for a deep reflection, on the transformative potential of a green economy, that favors the development of new jobs based on ecology and care for the environment “green jobs” and sustainable agriculture in the current global environment, inviting us to explore the synergies between environmental conservation and development economic as fundamental pillars of a sustainable future for all.

CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR AGRICULTURE IN DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

Regarding the challenges and opportunities for a more developed and sustainable agriculture in Latin America, it analyzes how globalization impacts nation states, focusing on three main aspects: trade openness, foreign direct investment and capital mobility. Therefore, the factors that

can influence the formulation of public policies are addressed, highlighting the need for countries to adopt strategies that allow them to better integrate into the global economy [5].

In this way, it explores the challenges that imply the loss of economic sovereignty and the risks of dependence on global markets, but also identifies opportunities, such as access to greater investment flows and broader markets. In addition, it addresses concepts such as the "trilemma of the global economy", which states that globalization, democracy and the nation State cannot coexist simultaneously in their maximum expression, forcing us to choose between them in different configurations.

This also reveals specific cases of Latin America and the influence of international organizations on the local economy, with examples such as the crises in Europe and the IMF policies in Mexico, which show the tensions between the global market and national priorities. In this regard, the emerging problems and trends of agriculture in the global context are analyzed, especially after the food crises of 2007-2008. It especially addresses the Global Food Crisis, which highlights the volatility in food prices that caused an increase in poverty and social mobilizations, known as "hunger revolts," mainly in countries in Africa, Asia and Latin America, underlining the fragility of agricultural systems in the face of external shocks [3].

Furthermore, about climate change and its impact, it explains how global warming affects agricultural productivity through extreme phenomena such as droughts and floods, threatening food security, especially in vulnerable regions. It also takes into account as another additional factor the increase in population, with a projection of 9 billion inhabitants by 2050, highlighting the need to adapt agriculture to meet the growing demand for food.

Another relevant point is Investment in agriculture, since The World Bank and other entities advocate for greater investment in the agricultural systems of developing countries, considering their potential to reduce poverty and promote sustainable development. Thus, it establishes the role of technology and cooperation as a vitally important strategy; which mentions the importance of advances in seeds, sustainable practices such as direct sowing and the support of governments and private entities to increase agricultural efficiency and mitigate global inequalities.

In essence, it reflects on how to balance the growth of agricultural production with sustainability and social justice in a context of interrelated crises: energy, financial and ecological.

Regarding the so-called “Green marketing” that contributes with its efforts to care and preserve the environment with sustainable businesses, it has been possible to demonstrate

how companies can integrate marketing strategies that prioritize environmental sustainability, balancing the needs of the business. and the expectations of conscious consumers [1]. Thus, mention is made of some main aspects such as:

- **Green marketing**

It can serve as a tool to preserve the environment through the development of sustainable products and services that reduce the ecological impact. However, it raises problems associated with Greenwashing: It identifies the practice of greenwashing (when companies appear to be more sustainable than they really are) as a key challenge that can erode consumer trust.

- **Research and perceptions**

Based on a mixed research approach, the study evaluates the perspectives of companies, experts and consumers in Pereira, Colombia, highlighting the interest in implementing sustainable marketing strategies.

- **The Proposals for Sustainable Businesses**

Offers practical and theoretical recommendations to help companies transition towards sustainable business models by integrating green marketing into their operations.

The article highlights the importance of regulated and ethical strategies to transform the way in which companies contribute to environmental care and how this can generate competitive advantages in global markets.

KEY CONCEPTS: SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Sustainable agriculture and economic development are intrinsically linked, especially in the context of developing countries. In this sense, the World Bank points out that, in many emerging economies, agriculture constitutes the basis of economic development. This report indicates that “sustainable agriculture can be a catalyst for reducing poverty and improving food security, provided that comprehensive policies that support small farmers are implemented” [12].

Understanding the key concepts of this relationship allows us to design effective strategies to achieve inclusive and resilient growth. This indicates that sustainable agriculture refers to an approach to agricultural production that seeks to meet current food needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs. This implies a balance between productivity, the conservation of natural resources and social well-being.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, agricultural sustainability includes practices that maintain soil health, biodiversity and water resources, while maximizing the resilience of agricultural systems to climate change, including as principles: The efficient and responsible use of natural resources, such as water and soil; Crop diversification to improve food

security and reduce economic risks; Reduction in the use of pesticides and chemical fertilizers to minimize environmental impact; and Integration of local practices with innovative technologies. [2]

Likewise, the crucial role of family farming in the fight against hunger and poverty is analyzed, especially in the context of developing countries. The authors explore how this agricultural model contributes to sustainable development through local practices that protect the environment and strengthen rural economies. They also identify challenges such as the lack of institutional support and propose strategies to enhance their impact on food security. [10]

On the other hand, the use of Integrated Nutritional Management (INM) is examined as an essential strategy for sustainability in agriculture. MNI combines mineral fertilizers with organic options such as legumes, crop residues, industrial by-products and bio fertilizers. This approach seeks to improve agricultural productivity, maintain soil quality, and reduce environmental impact by reducing exclusive dependence on chemical fertilizers. Their study addresses aspects such as the physical, chemical and biological quality of the soil, crop productivity, plant health and economic efficiency. In addition, it emphasizes how this method can contribute to addressing global challenges in agriculture, such as the growing demand for food and the impacts of climate change. [4]

CREATION OF GREEN JOBS AND STRENGTHENING OF RURAL COMMUNITIES.

The creation of green jobs linked to sustainable practices in rural communities has a transformative impact in both economic and social terms. These jobs, related to activities such as sustainable agriculture, renewable energy, ecotourism and environmental management, offer a double advantage: improving the economic conditions of rural communities and contributing to the mitigation of climate change.

Based on what has been proposed by various authors, the importance of green employment in the transition towards a more sustainable economy is addressed, especially in the Latin American context. This concept of green employment is central to economic reactivation, since it not only proposes creating new jobs in key sectors such as energy efficiency and waste management, but also seeks to improve the working conditions of the most vulnerable sectors. [6]

Likewise, the authors highlight the urgent need to implement public policies that promote this type of employment in urban and suburban areas. In addition, they highlight that the creation of green jobs could help reduce social and economic inequality, which has been exacerbated by the global health and economic crisis. The promotion of a "just transition", which aims at sustainability and

environmental protection, is seen as an opportunity to improve both working conditions and the well-being of communities.

This approach also highlights the urgency for local governments to act to mitigate the impacts of climate change and support the regeneration of ecosystems, which is particularly relevant in a continent like Latin America, which faces high levels of climate vulnerability and social inequality. The need for a coordinated response between authorities and citizens is essential to achieve a more fair and sustainable recovery.

II. DISCUSSION

How can sustainable agriculture alternatives improve economic development in Latin American nations?

In response to this question, the problem of climate change in Latin America and its impact on agriculture is considered, as a fundamental sector for the economy and the livelihood of the population. From there, the negative effects of climate change on agricultural production are linked, such as the decrease in productivity, the loss of biodiversity and the intensification of extreme weather events. [9]

The generalized opinions of many authors converge when thinking about the need for a transition towards sustainable agriculture, to mitigate the effects of climate change and guarantee food security in Latin American countries. So that different sustainable agricultural practices, such as agroecology, integrated pest and disease management, soil conservation and efficient use of water, are presented as alternatives to adapt to climate change and improve the resilience of agricultural systems.

At the same time, some researchers look for a key strategy in the association of crops for the development of sustainable agriculture. It is argued that the association of crops, also known as polyculture, offers a series of environmental, economic and social benefits that contribute to the sustainability of the agricultural system.

This highlights the ability of intercropping systems to increase biodiversity, improve soil health, reduce erosion and nutrient loss, control pests and diseases more naturally, and increase water use efficiency. In addition, it is mentioned that the association of crops can contribute to the diversification of production, increase profitability for farmers and improve food security. [11]

CHALLENGES FOR THE IMPLEMENTATION OF SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURE IN LATIN AMERICA

According to a preliminary and critical review of literature on the challenges facing sustainable agriculture in Latin America. Thus, the challenges faced when making decisions about agriculture in Latin America consider a level of 53% for the lack of support from Public Policies towards

sustainable agriculture, 14% corresponds to the financing of sustainable agriculture, Approximately 12% is allocated to the use of technology, promotion of research and technological investment, while 2% represents access to new markets, 2% is attributed to adaptation to climate change, 9% of the resources is intended for training and only 8% distributed between incentives and infrastructure that show the absence of public policies. [7]

Figure 1. Challenges for Sustainable Agriculture in Latin America

These results make important statements and demonstrate a series of obstacles that prevent the adoption of sustainable practices in Latin America, including:

• **Lack of access to technology and knowledge**

The majority of Latin American farmers do not have access to sustainable production technologies and practices, limiting their options to improve efficiency and reduce environmental impact.

• **Limitations in accessing new markets**

Farmers face difficulties in accessing new markets that value sustainable products, making sustainable practices difficult to make profitable.

• **Difficulties in Accessing financing**

Lack of access to financing limits farmers' ability to invest in technologies and infrastructure that allow them to adopt sustainable practices.

• **Lack of Public Policies that Promote Sustainable Agriculture**

The absence of public policies that support and promote sustainable agriculture makes it difficult to adopt sustainable practices on a large scale.

III. CONCLUSIONS

There are various alternative solutions not only to generate sustainable agriculture as an economic engine for Latin American countries but also to adapt to climate change, this shows that the participation of local actors, investment in research and development, is significantly required. and the creation of public policies that promote the green economy, this effort demands inter-institutional collaboration and the transfer of knowledge to promote the adoption of

sustainable agricultural practices and strengthen the capacity to adapt to climate change in the agricultural sector.

One of the most successful sustainable practices is crop association as an innovative strategy that considers factors such as complementarity between species, spatial distribution of plants, nutrient management and crop rotation to achieve an effective crop association. viable and promising alternative for the development of sustainable agriculture, which seeks to balance productivity with environmental protection and social well-being.

In terms of employment, green sectors allow diversifying job opportunities in areas where conventional agriculture or livestock farming are traditionally the main sources of income. This change not only creates jobs, but also encourages technical skills training and the adoption of innovative technologies. This implies the need to address the challenges facing sustainable agriculture and promote a green economy in Latin American agriculture. Also, through the implementation of programs that provide access to technology, knowledge, markets and financing, as well as the creation of public policies that encourage the adoption of sustainable practices, sustainable practices can be promoted and the impact on the planet's ecosystems reduced.

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